

Brexit's Impact on UK Pharmaceutical and Medical Device Regulation

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Abstract

Brexit has transformed the United Kingdom's pharmaceutical and medical device regulatory framework, shifting authority from the European Medicines Agency (EMA) to the Medicines and Healthcare products Regulatory Agency (MHRA). With full independence, MHRA introduced new pathways to accelerate patient access to medicines, including the Innovative Licensing and Access Pathway (ILAP), Rolling Review, and a 150-day national assessment route. Centrally authorized products now require conversion to Great Britain Marketing Authorizations, while medical devices transitioned from the CE mark to the UKCA mark. These changes, alongside collaborations with International Council for Harmonisation (ICH) countries, aim to ensure timely availability of safe and effective products. Early outcomes suggest the UK is positioning itself as a leader in pharmaceutical innovation and regulation, with faster approvals and streamlined processes. However, given the short timeframe since Brexit, the full impact of MHRA's independent role remains to be seen, with long-term effects likely to emerge in the coming years.

Key Words: EMA, Regulatory Agency, ICH, pharmaceutical innovation, MHRA

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INTRODUCTION

One of the most significant events in recent European history has been Brexit, the phrase used to characterize the UK's exit from the European Union. Both before and after the departure, there have been substantial repercussions from the UK's exit from the EU. The UK was a full member of the EU before Brexit, with all the responsibilities and rights that entailed. This comprised access to the single market and customs union of the EU as well as unrestricted movement of goods, people, and capital. The UK played a crucial role in the decision-making process as an EU member. In the EU government, there were powerful roles held by UK representatives. The UK officially exited the EU on January 31st, 2020, and is no longer a member, losing its influence in the decision-making process and its ability to influence EU policy.

Although there are many different and intricate reasons for Brexit, some of the most significant ones are worries about immigration, the loss of national sovereignty to EU institutions, and dissatisfaction with the bureaucratic rules of the EU. Also, some voters believed that the UK was not receiving a fair return on its contributions to the EU budget and that the country's economic progress was being stifled by membership in the EU. A referendum that has major historical ramifications for the UK was held on June 23, 2016. By casting a vote, the British people chose whether it would be better for the UK to exit the European Union or stay a member. The agreement was divided into three parts: the UK will restrict access to the social security system for EU migrant workers. New immigrants are prohibited from receiving social assistance for four years following their date of entry. On June 23, 2016, 51.9% of voters cast ballots in favor of leaving the EU. On January 31, 2020, the UK formally left the EU, and the transition period ended on December 31, 2020. Standardization served as yet another crucial factor. The EU setting numerous regulations for items' sizes, shapes, and other factors infuriates the British. EU lawyers are confident that having a single European standard is far more practical and beneficial than having 28 national standards. Opponents of the country's membership in the EU, on the other hand, think that everything should be under national control, particularly in the areas of security, employment, and health. It's thought that Britain's departure from the EU could have a "domino effect." That is, other EU member states will want to leave. That will weaken the EU position and strengthen Russia's position in the geopolitical arena.

AIM

The aim was to compare the regulatory requirements for drugs and medical devices in United Kingdom regulatory body Medicines and Healthcare Regulatory Agency (MHRA) between Pre and Post Brexit phases.

OBJECTIVE

This investigation aims to examine the evolving regulatory framework for medicines and medical devices in Europe and the United Kingdom. It covers marketing authorization procedures for drugs in Europe, regulatory pathways for medical devices in the EU, and the new requirements introduced in the UK post-Brexit. The study also highlights how these procedures are impacting compliance, identifies which have become more stringent, and evaluates their usefulness and overall effect on regulatory practices.

Plan of Work:

Stage 1:

Explaining about the Brexit and giving an introduction to the title and its impact on healthcare in humans.

Stage 2:

Knowing about the old regulatory procedures when being a member of the European MemberState and its role in the regulation of medicinal products and devices.

Stage 3:

Looking into the new regulatory pathways that are been followed and the new strategies that are set by the MHRA regulatory body.

Stage 4:

Comparison of both the regulatory procedures and identifying the changes.

Stage 5:

Concluding with the comparison of the two scenarios, analyzing the changes, a look into the performance of the independent regulatory working group after the exit from the European Member State and identifying the stringent pathway.

Methodology:

Pre-procedural step	
Before day-14	Applicant discussions with RMS. RMS allocates procedure number.
Day-14	Submission of the dossier to the RMS and CMSs. Validation of the application using RMS/CMS validation checklist for human medicinal products in DCP. Positive validation by CMS

Assessment step-I	
Day 0	RMS starts the procedure.
Day 70	RMS forwards the Preliminary Assessment Report on the dossier to the dossier to the CMSs and the applicant.
Until day 100	CMSs send their comments to the RMS, CMSs and applicant. It

	may also be sufficient for the CMS to indicate in CTS only incase there are no additional comments.
Until day 105	<p>Consultation between RMS and CMSs and applicant.</p> <p>If consensus not reached RMS stops the clock to allow applicant to supplement the dossier and respond to the questions.</p>
Clock-stop period	<p>Applicant may send draft responses to the RMS and agrees the date with the RMS and agrees the date with the RMS for submission of the final response. Applicant sends the final response document to the RMS and CMSs within a period of 3 months, which can be extended by a further 3 months.</p>
Day 106	<p>RMS restarts the procedure following the receipt of a final response of a final response or expiry of the agreed clock-stop period if a response has not been received. The CMSs are informed via e-mail and CTS will be updated accordingly.</p>

Assessment step II	
Day 120	RMS sends the DAR, draft labelling and draft PL to CMSs and the applicant. The quality assessor at the RMS completes a product surveillance risk assessment template, if applicable. This risk assessment is designed to provide information for post-marketing surveillance analysis by Official Medicines Control Laboratories.
Day 145	CMSs send comments to RMS, CMSs and the applicant. It may also be sufficient for the CMS to indicate in CTS only in case there are no additional comments.
Day 150	RMS may close procedure if consensus reached.

	Proceed to national 30 days step for granting MA.
Day 160	Applicant sends the response document to CMSs and RMS.
Until 180	If consensus is not reached by day 150, RMS to communicate outstanding issues with applicant, receive any additional clarification, prepare a short report and forward it to the CMSs and the applicant.
Day 195	A Break-Out Session (BOS) may be held at the European Medicines Agency with the involvement of MSs to reach consensus on the major outstanding issues.
Between day 195 and 210	RMS consults with the CMSs and the applicant to discuss the remaining comments raised.

Day 210	<p>If consensus is reached</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In case of positive position from RMS, closure of procedure including end of procedure letter final day 210 overview AR, SmPC, labelling and PL, active substance and finished product specifications and proceed to national 30 days step for granting the MA. • In case of negative position from the RMS closure of the <p>procedure negatively. The end of procedure letter and final day 210 overview AR is circulated.</p>
At the latest within 7 days after day 210	<p>If consensus on a positive RMS AR was not reached at day 210 the point of disagreement submitted by CMS will be referred by the RMS to the CMDh for resolution.</p>

National step	
7 Days after close of procedure	Applicant sends high quality national translations of SmPC, labelling and PL to CMSs and RMS.
30 Days after close of the procedure	Granting of national marketing authorization in RMS and CMSs if outcome is positive and there is no referral to the CMDh. Agencies will adopt the decision and will issue the marketing authorization subject to submission of acceptable translations.
30 Days after close of CMD referral procedure	Granting of national marketing authorization in RMS and CMSs if positive conclusion by the CMDh and no referral to the CHMP.

FLOWCHART OF MUTUAL RECOGNITION PROCEDURE

MEDICAL PRODUCTS USED IN COMBINATION WITH MEDICAL DEVICES

TABLE 2: REGULATION: EU DIRECTIVE 2001/83/EC OR REGULATION NO 726/2004.

Type of combination	Illustration	Conformity Assessment of Devices
Integral	Medical Product and device form a single integrated product. Examples include: pre filled syringes and pens, patches for transdermal drug delivery,	MA should include a CE certificate for the device or if not, CE marked but would need to be certified. if marketed separately, applicant must include an

	pre filled inhalers.	opinion from a notified body on conformity of devices. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Requirements does not apply to class I Devices.
Co-packaged or obtained separately	Medical product and device are separate items and contained in same pack or obtained separately. Example include: reusable pen for insulin cartridges tablet delivery system with controller for pain management	Must be CE marked in accordance with EU medical devices legislation.

CE CERTIFICATION PROCESS

STEP 1: Identify the applicable directives

The first step is to identify whether the product can be CE marked or not. Not all products are required to be CE marked, only the products that fall within the scope of at least one of the CE Marketing Directives. There are more than 20 product directives and regulations covering a range of products.

STEP 2: Identify the applicable requirements of the directives

Each directive has slightly different methods of demonstrating conformity. This usually depends on the classification of the product and its intended use. Every directive has a number of essential requirements which the product has to meet.

STEP 3: Identify an appropriate route to conformity

The CE Marking process is always a self-declaration process however you may need to involve a third party. This is set out in the 'system of attestation' and will vary between Directive. Some products (such as invasive medical devices or fire alarm systems) may, to some extent, have a mandatory requirement for some involvement of an authorized third party.

STEP 4: ASSESSMENT OF THE PRODUCTS CONFIRMITY

When all the requirements have been established, you need evidence that the product meets the essential requirements of the Directives. This usually involves some assessment and testing. It will often involve ensuring that the requirements of the applicable harmonized standards, which were identified in step 2, have been met.

STEP 5: COMPILE THE TECHNICAL DOCUMENTATION:

Technical documentation relating to the product or range of products needs to be compiled. This information should cover every aspect relating to conformity and is likely to include details of the design, development and manufacture of the product. Technical documentation may also be known as the Technical File or Technical Construction File. Technical documentation can be made available in any format and must be held for a period up to 10 years after the manufacture of the last unit, and in most cases reside in the European Economic Area (EEA).

STEP 6: MAKE A DECLARATION AND AFFIX THE CE MARK

When the manufacturer, importer or authorized representative is satisfied that their product conforms to the applicable CE marking directives, they must complete a declaration. Under most directives it is known as the EU Declaration of Conformity but other terms exist.

FIGURE 1 : Marketing authorization of different classes of medical devices

POST-BREXIT SCENARIO

The UK left the single market on January 1, 2021, bringing an uncertain year to an end, after its withdrawal from the European Union on January 31, 2020. This signified the cessation of the use of European institutions and law, which served as the foundation for many aspects of health and healthcare in the UK. Regulations Laws on the sale and purchase of healthcare, trade agreements, and immigration regulations that had previously applied to most of a continent were returned to the UK. The free flow of people, products, and services between the UK and the EU came to an end, and for the first time in at least 30 years, the UK government was

once again given carte blanche to reshape how all of these sectors operated. However, the 2020 Trade and Cooperation Agreement (TCA), along with the 2019 Withdrawal Agreement, which includes the Ireland/Northern Ireland Protocol, lays out the UK's new relationship with the EU and includes special provisions for Northern Ireland's de facto continued membership in the single market. These contracts include clauses addressing matters like pandemic management or the transportation of human organs that are directly related to health. The Health Foundation-funded Health and International Relations Monitor project's interim outcome is this report. It examines the effects of leaving the EU and altering foreign relations for health, taking into account both the past and the future expectations of the NHS, the government, and business leaders. The six core categories of pharmaceuticals and devices, international trade agreements, devolution, procurement, workforce, and Northern Ireland are all taken into account when looking at changes in the health sector. Our entire research, which will be released in the spring of 2019, will investigate in further detail how Brexit will affect the workforce and living standards, two of the most important pillars of health.

Figure 2: The use of ILAP in the MHRA

SUBMISSION TYPES

TABLE 3: THE TYPES OF VARIOUS PROJECT ORBIS SUBMISSIONS

TYPE	A	B	C
Submission timeline	Application submission before 1month of FDA submission	Application submission 1 month after FDA submission	Application submission any time after FDA action
Submission overlaps with FDA	Expected to do so	Expected to do so	Permitted to do
Sharing FDA reviews	Yes, FDA review is shared	Yes, FDA review is shared	YES shared

UKCA MARK

Medical devices that are being sold in Great Britain (England, Wales, and Scotland) are required to bear the UKCA (UK Conformity Assessed) product label. Relevant products need a CE marking to be sold in the EU, EEA, or Northern Ireland markets because the UKCA marking is not accepted there. Up to 30 June 2023, manufacturers of medical devices may use either the UKCA designation or the CE marking on the products they place on the British market. According to the overview above, the government expects to continue accepting CE- marked products in the United Kingdom after 30 June 2023. See the implementation update on efforts towards a strengthened future medical devices regime for additional information on these transitional measures. Medical devices placed on the market in Great Britain (England, Wales, and Scotland) may be marked with the UKCA mark. The Northern Ireland market will not accept the UKCA mark. For gadgets to be sold in Northern Ireland, they must have a CE certification or CE UKNI mark.

CLASS I MEDICAL DEVICES

You must declare in writing that the medical device conforms with the UK MDR 2002 standards. If your medical device uses sterile goods or has a measuring function, you must apply to an Approved Body (based in the UK) for approval and certification of the components of your manufacturing process that relate to sterility

or metrology. Once you've done this, you can add a UKCA mark to the goods and sell it.

CLASS II a MEDICAL DEVICES

To certify that your Class II a device complies with UK MDR 2002 specifications. The assessment may be examination and testing of each product or homogenous batch of products (Part II of the UK MDR 2002, Annex IV (as modified by Part II of Schedule 2A to the UK MDR 2002)), audit of the production quality assurance system (Part II of the UK MDR 2002, Annex V (as modified by Part II of Schedule 2A to the UK MDR 2002)), audit of final inspection and testing (Part II of the UK MDR 2002, Annex VI (as modified by Part II of Schedule 2A to the UK MDR 2002)), audit of the full quality assurance system (Part II of the UK MDR 2002, Annex II (as modified by Part II of Schedule 2A to the UK MDR 2002)).

CLASS II b MEDICAL DEVICES

If your device falls into this category, you must carry out either:

- a Part II of the UK MDR 2002, Annex II (as modified by Part II of Schedule 2A to the UK MDR 2002) audit of full quality assurance system or;
- a Part II of the UK MDR 2002, Annex III (as modified by Part II of Schedule 2A to the UK MDR 2002) type-examination plus either option 1, 2 or 3 given for the Class II a device above You can place a UKCA mark on your product and place it on the market when you have received a certificate from the Approved Body.

CLASS III MEDICAL DEVICES

If your device falls into this category, you must carry out either:

- a Part II of the UK MDR 2002, Annex II (as modified by Part II of Schedule 2A to the UK MDR 2002) audit of the full quality assurance system including a design dossier examination or;
- a Part II of the UK MDR 2002, Annex III (as modified by Part II of Schedule 2A to the UK MDR 2002) type-examination plus 1 of the option 1, 2 or 3 given for the Class IIa devices above
- You can place a UKCA mark on your product and place it on the market when you have received a certificate from the Approved Body.

EXEMPTIONS

Custom-made device, albeit it must still adhere to the UK MDR 2002 regulations and explicitly identify the sort of device. You must take care to ensure the health and safety of patients when undergoing a clinical inquiry. It must state "exclusively for clinical investigation" and meet all requirements, a medical instrument for in vitro diagnosis (IVD) used for performance assessment, a non-compliant gadget that is occasionally used for humanitarian reasons. Although Great Britain (England, Wales, and Scotland) will be free to use the UKCA mark, equipment sold in Northern Ireland will still require a CE marking and compliance with EU regulations. You must engage an EU-recognized Notified Body to carry out any necessary third-party conformity assessment if you want to have your device CE marked for usage in both Northern Ireland and the EU.

STEP BY STEP PROCEDURE

- STEP 1:** Check if product needs UKCA marking
- STEP 2:** Check the appropriate route for conformity assessment
- STEP 3:** Draft technical file and ensure compliance
- STEP 4:** Draw up draft UK declaration of conformity
- STEP 5:** Affix UKCA mark and prepare to place product in market
- STEP 6:** Identify a conformity assessment body
- STEP 7:** Draft technical documentation
- STEP 8:** Draw up a draft declaration of conformity
- STEP 9:** Place device in market officially

COMPARISON

TABLE 4: COMPARISON OF THE REGULATIONS BEFORE AND AFTER BREXIT

PRE-BREXIT REGULATIONS	POST-BREXIT REGULATIONS
<p>MARKETING AUTHORIZATION OF MEDICINES WHILE AN EU MEMBER STATE</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Centralized procedure • Decentralized procedure • Mutual Recognition Procedure <p>National Procedure</p>	<p>MARKETING AUTHORIZATION AFTER BREXIT</p> <p>For already available drugs:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Converting Centralized products ○ European Commission Decision Reliance Procedure ○ Decentralized and mutual recognition reliance procedure for marketing authorization

	<p>New routes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Innovative License Access Pathway • Rolling Review • 150-day assessment for national applications for medicines <p>New ICH countries collaboration programme:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Access Consortium • Planet Orbis
<p>MEDICAL DEVICE REGULATION BEING A EUROPEAN MEMBER STATE</p> <p>Regulation (EU)2017/745 -Medical devices</p> <p>Regulation (EU)2017/746-Invitro diagnostic medical devices</p> <p>CE MARKING</p>	<p>MEDICAL DEVICE REGULATION AFTER EXIT</p> <p>UK Medical device regulation 2002</p> <p>UKCA MARKING</p>

CONCLUSION

Brexit has been a very impactful step in the United Kingdom which has shown a drastic difference in the social, economic, healthcare and various other fields as it has come out totally from being a member state in each and every aspect. In this study the pharmaceutical sector and regulatory department for the pharmaceutical products regulations have been seen and compared. The old regulatory body of the UK was EMA and the MHRA was not having the full authority. Through the Brexit the MHRA has taken the full authority for the regulation of drugs and medical devices. The previous regulations for drugs which were followed prior to exiting from the EU includes centralized procedure, decentralized procedure, mutual recognition procedure, national procedure and for medical devices they followed the CE marking. After the exit they have adopted various new regulations in a aim of providing safety to the patients and healthcare of individuals. In case of drugs for novel medicines they have framed a new strategy which reduces time to market that

included ILAP Innovative License Access Pathway and Rolling Review. The other authorization routes are 150-day assessment for national application. For already approved drugs in the UK market they have to change their authorization in accordance or the product will be removed from market. All the centrally authorized products should be converted to Great Britain Marketing Authorization through the guidelines present. In case of the medical device regulation, they have brought in a new marking. The previously used CE mark was converted to UKCA mark. As the marking has changed there are also other procedures that are similar to the EU.

They have also made new collaboration programmes with ICH countries for the availability of medicines without any delay or problem. Through the new innovation methods various products have been marketed in short time. The UK has grown as a world leader in the development, manufacture, and regulation of pharmaceuticals after the Brexit. It has also made speedier approval of medicines in a safe and effective manner.

As the Brexit came into effect recently in around 2 years' time is insufficient to elucidate the positive and negative of the newly independent regulatory body. MHRA till now has shown early promising for quicker approval of innovative medicines. In the fourth coming years only the complete effect of exit can be identified.

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